

Project Facts

- Call identifier: H2020-SU-DS-2019
- Topic: SU-DS05-2018-2019 - Digital security, privacy, data protection and accountability in critical sectors
- EC Funding: 4 998 057,88 €
- Duration: 36 months
- Consortium: 15 partners
- Coordinator: Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece – Dr. Angelos Amditis (a.amditis@iccs.gr)

Pilot Facts & Goal

- Genova Italy
- Duration: 4 months
- Five scenarios realized in real conditions
- Training sessions for CERTs and CSIRTs
- Public demonstration sessions with: universities, schools, citizens, passengers, institutions & stakeholders, end-users

The main goal of the Genova Pilot was to validate all the CitySCAPE tools developed throughout the project among a precise set of scenarios that involved the two major topics of the pilot: information to passengers and digital ticketing. AMT mobile application, together with all the infomobility and ticketing infrastructure was involved in the testing scenarios.

